

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH TO DEVELOPING A SKILLS FRAMEWORK FOR DISTRIBUTED CONTEXTE

Khaoula SOLTANI ^{1*}, **Messaoud BENZOUAI** ¹ and **Mohamed Djamel MOUSS** ¹

Laboratory of Automation and Manufacturing , Department of Industrial Engineering, Faculty of Technology, University of Batna2- Mostefa Ben Boulaid , Batna 05000, Algeria. E-mail : k.soltani@univ-batna2.dz ; E-mail : m.benzouai@univ-batna2.dz, E-mail : m.mouss@univ-batna2.dz

ABSTRACT: *A human skills framework is a human resource management tool that identifies and describes the set of skills required to fill different positions within an organization. This article helps to identify the knowledge, know-how, and interpersonal skills needed for each role, thereby facilitating talent management and the professional development of employees. By clearly identifying the required skills and adequately training personnel, the framework helps reduce costs related to unexpected breakdowns and emergency interventions, while maximizing equipment availability. A human skills framework is a strategic tool that contributes to optimizing an organization's human capital, enabling better alignment between available and required skills, helping to minimize overall maintenance costs across the company.*

KEYWORDS: *Skills management, Skills model, Activities, Repository, Skills level, distributed maintenance.*

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent years have shown that despite the ever-increasing automation of production systems, the human entity remains one of the key points of the success and sustainability of a company in a highly changing environment. Therefore, it is essential for a manager to precisely identify the skills necessary for the proper functioning of his company and the personnel who carry them. Indeed, the efficiency of the processes largely depends on the proper allocation of the latter. Also, the maintenance department is made up of human resources. They are the ones who carry out maintenance activities. Generally, these resources have all the capacities to carry out their various interventions F.Monchy.[1] Depending on the characteristics of the activities and those of the resources, one of the difficulties of the maintenance department manager will be to assign the appropriate resource to each activity at the right time. To meet these challenges, companies have committed to a new vision reserving a prominent place for human capital management. The skills management component is then retained as one of the priority pillars of the strategy of these companies. Thus, only companies that have the permanent ability to reconfigure themselves, making their skills a central concern, will be able to ensure their sustainability.

In this context, the problem we address is a problem of scheduling and resource allocation in which the tasks are maintenance operations (preventive or corrective) and the resources are local or distributed maintenance teams. Tasks are characterized by skills required for their processing, while resources are characterized by a profile of acquired skills. In the models in the literature, differences in skills are rarely addressed. Resources are therefore often considered identical or having only one skill.

Due to the limit of the operational scope of the concept of competence, noted in the practices of organizations, we will first focus our attention on the in-depth analysis of the concept of competence and maintenance activities according to the degree of complexity in the distributed context. Secondly, we present skills management through the various works carried out on this theme in industrial engineering. Finally, in this particular area we propose a skills benchmark based on maintenance activities.

2 METHODS

2.1 Distributed system concept

A concept of distributed system was proposed by H. Kaffel et al.[2] According to him, there are four types of resources (human resources, material resources, spare parts and computer system). Each problem requires intervention by the maintenance

team. He also proposed that there are two possibilities for a company Fig.1.

Fig. 1 Concept of distributed maintenance

- Sharing;
- Sharing and collaboration.

The publications found relate to the logistics aspect B. Liao et al. [3] ; B. Miao et al.[4] ; D. Hedjazi et al. [5]; Z. Simeu-Abazi et al. [6]. Y. Bella. [7], The work R.D.Mezafacek. [8] touches on both the logistics and strategic aspects, the oldest dates from 2011. The authors propose for the first time a model adapted to distributed maintenance (Petri Net) and a method of evaluation and optimization of performances (maintenance cost and availability of production sites).

2.2 Classification of maintenance activities

The AFNOR X 60-000 standard F.Monchy. [9]; A.Seguy. [10] Proposes a classification of maintenance actions into five levels of complexity Table 1.

This table shows that resources are increasingly specialized and therefore increasingly expensive with the increase in the level of maintenance. In this case, the problem of adequate sizing and optimal allocation of resources in order to minimize the cost of maintenance operations remains. This problem arises more for a maintenance management system applied in a multi-site context. The first of the specificities related to maintenance is to assign tasks of different levels of complexity to human resources. Their differences stem from varying skill levels, which in turn affect their remuneration and, consequently, their labor costs.

Table 1. Five levels of maintenance.

Level	Intervention personnel	Required means	Documents
1	On-site operator (Operator-Adjuster)	Light tools defined in the operating instructions. Consumables.	Self maintenance procedures. Quality assurance procedures.

2	Technician or authorized operator on site (adjuster, line manager, etc.).	Light tools. Spare parts nearby without delay.	Detailed procedures. Maintenance instruction.
3	Qualified maintenance technician, on site or in the maintenance local.	Equipment provided. Measuring, testing and control devices.	Detailed procedures. Machine file.
4	Team of specialized technicians, in central workshop. Specialized company.	Specialized tools. Testing and control equipment. Spare parts and sub-assemblies.	Machine file. Specific documents. Preparation document.
5	Equipment manufacturer. Specialized company.	Logistical means close to manufacturing by the manufacturer.	Manufacturer documentation (Specific).

This amounts to saying that the levels of Acquired Operational Skills (AOS) by human resources must adapt to the levels of Required Operational Skills (ROS) by the activity.

2.3 Human resources in maintenance and their skills

The resources of the maintenance department are mainly qualified personnel for the various interventions. However, they also need tools and, for repairs, spare parts and maintenance consumables. The most important resources of the maintenance department, but also the most complicated to manage, are human resources.

AFNOR gives the following definition of skills: "A skill is the implementation, in a professional situation, of capacities that allow a function or activity to be properly carried out". To characterize AOSs by human resources and ROSs by activity, we consider the concepts developed by the M.Harzallah. [11] Model, where on the one hand, there appears the concept of what is acquired by individuals, described as "acquired skills" so that they can perform an activity and on the other hand, an activity requires a set of "required skills" in order to be able to be performed.

In addition, Skills have an undeniable impact on quality, lead times and production costs. In addition,

they allow for increased flexibility in the production system. Hence the need to take into account the skills of human operators and to seek their adequacy with the skills required by the workstations or functions they occupy R.Frere. [12].

To schedule maintenance activities in an industrial context, D.Hedjazi et al. [13] Proposes a systemic and operational approach. It emphasizes the importance of integrating resource and skills constraints into the planning process, while providing monitoring tools to ensure continuous improvement.

The work of B.Dakkak et al. [14] Highlights the importance of identifying, developing and optimizing skills to build a sustainable and high-performing system.

2.4 Approach adopted

2.4.1 Human resources management

Skills management is a strategic issue for many companies. It is no longer enough to be aware of the skills available within the company; it is necessary to be able to determine the needs (recruitment, training, etc.). In order to manage staff more flexibly according to their skills, a methodology for developing a skills repository has been developed. This approach classifies skills into several types: Skills in relation to tasks, in relation to machines F.Croci et al.[15]; mixed skills G.L. Vairaktarakis .[16]; skills by contract H.V.Kher. [17]; skills by team of workers B.Grabot et al .[18] and finally, hierarchical skills R.Hung.[19]; A.Billionnet.[20], which are sorted and classified according to their importance and type, a hierarchical order is assigned to them. In this paper, we consider the last type of competence namely hierarchical competences (ROS and AOS), while considering the hypothesis: "for any maintenance intervention, the level of OSA by HR is just equal to the level of ROS by the activity".

However, if the AOS level of each HR and that of the ROS by activity are known, another problem appears, namely: the balancing of the workload between this HRs.

2.4.2 The skills framework

The skills framework describes all the skills required to carry out a given activity. It allows the company to identify its current and future skills needs. A tool for dialogue and consultation, the skills framework is developed in agreement with the interested parties and the people concerned by the A.Guittet. [21].

To align human skills with the requirements of Lean environments, Q.Wafae et al.[22] work to design a skills framework adapted to the context of Lean Management.

P.C.Loures et al. [23] Proposing a methodological framework for the implementation of autonomous maintenance by integrating the HTO (Human-Technological-Organizational) approach. This framework aims to optimize the management and efficiency of maintenance activities by taking into account the interactions between human, technological and organizational factors.

2.4.3 The methodology for developing the skills framework

According to A.Boumane et al. [24] the development is based on seven stages Fig. 2.

Fig. 1 Concept of distributed maintenance

a) Identify and analyze the activity

The identification and rigorous analysis of key activities makes it possible to structure the work, prioritize actions, and guarantee results aligned with the strategic objectives of the company.

b) Define performance indicators and criteria for the proper performance of the activity

The criteria for proper performance emphasize the methods and professional practices that ensure the activity is conducted correctly. They establish the required procedures for carrying out the activity, guaranteeing that these methods and practices align with established standards and expectations.

c) Identify the required skills

To identify the skills required in a distributed context, it is essential to consider several types of skills as well as appropriate assessment methods. There are several methods for identifying skills such as:

- **Job Analysis:** Break down the specific activities of a job to identify the skills needed. This helps you understand what is expected and what skills are required for each task.
- **Interviews with industry experts:** Consulting industry professionals can reveal tacit skills that are essential for success in a particular field.

- **Skills Matrix:** This tool helps you map and assess the key skills required for each role within the company.

d) Prioritize skills

The activity requires a certain level of skill. So, we must take this variability according to the complexity and level of the activity with respect to the process.

Level 1: Novice.

Level 2: Advanced Beginner.

Level 3: Proficient.

Level 4: The Efficient

Level 5: Expert.

e) Define resources

For each identified skill, it is essential to allocate the necessary resources. Then, it is appropriate to group together the resources common to several skills. This approach has several advantages. First, it highlights the resources that each actor must possess and those that he must master (whether hardware or software) to act competently. Then, it provides elements for reflection to better guide possible training.

f) Design an evaluation system

Referring to the activity-oriented competence model and the work of Le G. Le Boterf. [25], G. Le Boterf [26] we distinguish three assessment approaches:

- An approach linked to the performance achieved. The competence is assessed based on the performance indicators of the activity;
- An approach linked to the criteria of good performance. The person is competent if he or she manages to carry out the activity according to recognized practices and the criteria of good performance set;
- An approach linked to resources, this is the best-known approach. The person is assessed according to the resources possessed (knowledge, know-how, skills and qualities).

g) Classify skills

The skills framework is often presented in the form of a list. The concern to make it readable and operational requires a categorization of these elements. We have proposed a method of classifying skills that is based on the typology: the hierarchical skill Required Operational Skills (ROS) and Acquired Operational Skills (AOS). While considering the hypothesis: "for any maintenance intervention, the level of the AOS by HR is just equal to the level of the ROS by the activity".

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Once the seven steps have been completed, we synthesize the results in a document called, skills reference. Tables 2 and 3, It constitutes the database (framework) of ROSs by maintenance activities Table 2 and AOSs by human resources Table 3.

A maintenance activity is divided into several trades, each representing the type of work required to carry out this activity. The execution of a maintenance task may require one or more of these trades. In turn, the trades are broken down into specific operational skills required. In our case, it is important to specify the following elements: the level required for each of the Required Operational Skills (ROS) in Table 2a, the estimated intervention time in hours for the execution of each ROS in Table 2b. All the ROS listed in Table 2 constitute the benchmark of skills required for the activity. We remind you that level 1 of maintenance is the responsibility of the machine operator.

The concept of human resources competence is defined by the combination of several parameters, namely: knowledge (knowledge), know-how (abilities), and know-how (attitudes), as well as the level of experience, training, and other elements. It is on the basis of these parameters that operational skills are assessed. In our context, the level of human resources competence is divided into five levels: novice (level 1), advanced beginner (level 2), competent (level 3), efficient (level 4) and expert (level 5), as described in the model proposed by S.E.Dreyfus et al.[27] It is also necessary to fill in the boxes concerning the level acquired for each skill of a human resources professional Table 3a as well as the hourly rate specific to each professional for each Associated Operational Competence (AOC) Table 3b.

Table 2. Extracts from the Required Operational Skills (ROS) framework documents

a. Extract: Professions /OSR/ Levels of complexity (2,3,4,5).

Jobs	Required Operational Skills					
	ROS1	ROS2	ROS3	ROS4	ROS5	...
Electro-Pneumatics	2				3	
Mechanical-Hydraulics			2		5	
Automatic, Instrumentation				5		
Pipe Welding		3				
Methods Office					2	

b. Extract: Trades /OSR/tij: Estimated duration of intervention (hour).

Jobs	Required Operational Skills					
	RO S1	RO S2	RO S3	RO S4	RO S5	...
Electro-Pneumatics	2,5				4,2	
Mechanical-Hydraulics					1,5	
Automatic, Instrumentation			2,5			
Pipe Welding		2,1				
Methods Office				1,5		

Table 3. Extracts from the Acquired Operational Skills Frameworks (AOS)

a. HR / AOS / Levels acquired by HR.

Human resources	Operational Skills Acquired				
	OSA 1	OSA 2	OSA 3	OSA 4	OSA 5
LHR1	2				3
LHR2					5
LHR3		2		4	
.....					
CFT/HR1				4	
CFT/HR2					5
.....					
.					

b. HR / COA / Specific hourly rate (DA/hour)

Human resources	Operational Skills Acquired				
	OSA 1	OSA 2	OSA 3	OSA 4	OSA 5
LHR1	1000			1300	
LHR2				2000	
LHR3					17000
.....					
CFT/HR1					2500
CFT/HR2				1000	
.....					
.					

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Building a skills framework in a distributed context is an essential methodological approach to optimizing skills management within an organization. This process not only clarifies skills expectations, but also adapts training and professional practices to the specificities of the work situations encountered.

By integrating an approach based on all AOS levels by human resources and ROS levels by activity, it becomes possible to define skills directly related to the actual tasks performed by professionals. This promotes a better match between

field needs and training objectives, while taking into account geographical and organizational specificities.

The proposed methodology, structured around several key steps, facilitates the classification and assessment of the necessary skills. By focusing on the analysis of professional situations, it makes it possible to identify typical skills that are both relevant and applicable in the specific context of each agent.

In conclusion, this methodological contribution to the construction of a skills framework in a distributed context represents a strategic lever to improve collective and individual performance. It ensures better preparation of agents for field challenges while strengthening their commitment to the learning and professional development process. A well-defined skills framework makes it possible to structure maintenance activities by identifying the skills required for each task, which directly influences the efficiency and cost of intervention.

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7 NOTATION

The following symbols are used in this paper:
 ROS= Required Operational Skills.
 AOS=Acquired Operational Skills.
 HR= Human Resources.
 CFT= Central Flying Team.